

INDUSTRIA PLASTIC MELTING PLANT TWO-PHASE MACHINE GIVEN RISE TO BALANCE THREE-PHASE MACHINE USING TWO-PHASE TRANSFORMER

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14235842>

Abstract: *Industrial plastic melting plant two-phase machine given rise to balance three-phase machine using two-phase transformer is presented. It is more economical to generate and transmit three-phase power as two-phase power has been replaced by three-phase power. The needs for many industrial plastic melting plants operating on two-phase machine to give rise to balance three-phase machine and its operating characteristics cannot be ignored due to its superiority. Industrial plastic melting plant two-phase machine given rise to balance three-phase machine using two-phase transformer that were connected to convert two-phase machine to three-phase machine that gives rise to a balanced three-phase machine system. Less wires were used in three-phase transmission line than in two-phase line and no return current needed in a balanced three-phase circuit unlike in a balanced two-phase circuit and no fourth return wire is necessary. Power supplied to each of the three phase machines is pulsating in nature which shows that the total three-phase power supplied to a balanced three-phase machine circuit is constant. Because, three-phase machines and control equipment are smaller, lighter in weight, and more efficient than single or two-phase equipment of the same rated capacity. As one phase of 400V input power was open, it was no longer two-phase output. As the phase excites transformer 'T₁', the transformer which uses only part of the primary winding opened and it becomes a single-phase output from the secondary of transformer T₂. It becomes balanced three-phase machine system; thus, voltages and currents become equal and display 120 degrees electrically from each other. The voltages and currents become equal and displaced 90 degrees from each other. Voltage is maximum in one phase when it is zero in the other. The current is maximum in one phase when it is zero in the other. When any other two phases were opened, both secondary output voltages became unbalanced and badly distorted. This was detected with an oscilloscope that was used to monitor the output voltages when one of the primary phases was opened. Recommend for Industrial plastic melting plant machine operators and plant managers.*

Keywords: *Transformer, Plastic, Melting, Pulsating, two-phase, three-phase, excites,*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Industrial plastic melting plant two-phase machine given rise to balance three-phase machine using two-phase transformer is presented. The two-phase power and machine were wide-spread in industry some years ago. Two-phase power has since been replaced by three-phase power. The needs for many

industrial plastic melting plants operating on two-phase machine to give rise to balance three-phase machine and its operating characteristics cannot be ignored due to its superiority. Industrial plastic melting plant two-phase machine given rise to balance three-phase machine using two-phase transformer of the two transformers were connected in such a way to convert two-phase machine to three -phase machine that gives rise to a balanced three-phase machine system. In three-phase transmission line less wires were used than in two-phase line and no return current needed in a balanced three-phase circuit unlike in a balanced two-phase circuit thus, is not necessary to have fourth return wire. Although, the power supplied to each of the three phase machines was pulsating. There was a constant three-phase power supplied to a balanced three-phase machine circuit. Three-phase machines and control equipment are smaller, lighter in weight, and more efficient than single or two-phase equipment of the same capacity. [1, 3]

Three-phase machines is differs from a two-phase motor in that, it is smaller in size and may be used on industrial machines. A two-phase motor is a system that has two voltages at 90 degrees apart, which is no longer in use nowadays. The alternator is composed of two windings placed at 90 degrees from each other. A three-phase motor is an electric machine that transforms electric power into mechanical energy by means of electromagnetic interactions. Some electric motors are reversible and they can transform mechanical energy into electric power acting as generators. The plastics industry manufactures polymer materials called plastics and offers services in plastics important to a range of industries, including packaging, building and construction, electronics, aerospace, manufacturing and transportation. It may be referred to as part of the chemical industry.

The Industrial plastic melting plant two-phase machine given rise to balance three-phase machine using two-phase transformer has exist requirements for two-phase power in the small motor control field that may be necessary to convert a three-phase machine to two-phase. Changes may be made from two-phase to three-phase machine or from three-phase to two-phase machine with or without a change in voltage, by means of special transformers that has the required transformation ratio. Two single-phase transformers and Scott connections were used for the changed and. balanced to occurs in three-phase machine, the voltages and currents are all equal and displaced by 120 degrees from each other. The voltages and currents are also balanced two-phase system and equal but displaced 90 electrical degrees from each other. [2, 3] Voltage was high in one phase when it is zero in the other and similarly when the current is maximum in one phase when it is zero in the other.

2.0 Research experiment was carried out in UNIPORT Standard Laboratory

Experiment was carried out in UNIPORT standard research laboratory and the following, instrument, tools and components were used: Two Transformer, Resistance, Capacitor Run Motor, Power Supply, AC Metering Ammeter, AC Metering Voltmeter, and Connection Leads.

Special Precaution is due to be observed because of the present of high voltage in laboratory experiment. Connections are not permitted with the power 'ON' and all power should be turned "OFF" after completing each measurement and the results taken.

The circuit was connected as Scott configuration as shown in figure. 1. Connections to taps 3 and 8 on T_1 , and taps 3, 7 and 4 on T_2 were noted. Winding ratios were chosen for a balanced two-phase machine output. The transformer inputs were connected to the variable voltage 400V, 3 ϕ output terminals 4, 5 and 6, of the power supply

Figure 1: Scott connection configuration Transformation

Variable resistance was adjusted for $R_1 = R_2 = 170\Omega$, power supply was switched “ON” and adjust for a line-to-line voltage of 400Vac, three input line currents I_4 , I_5 and I_6 were record as $I_4 = 0.43 Aac$, $I_5 = 0.43 Aac$, $I_6 = 0.43 Aac$, returned to zero and power supply was turned “OFF”, three line currents were observed to be well balanced.

The two current meters A_5 and A_6 were removed from the input circuit and one was placed in series with the load resistors R_1 , and R_2 as shown by the virtual lines in figure1. Power supply was switched “ON” and line-to-line voltage was adjusted for 400Vac. Voltages across, and the currents through, the two load resistances R_1 and R_2 were measure and record as: $E_1 = 106 Vac$, $I_1 = 0.58 Aac$, and $E_2 = 110 Vac$, $I_2 = 0.62 Aac$

Voltage was return to zero and power supply was switch “OFF” and load currents and voltages were well balanced.

Powers in each load resistance are: $P_1 = E_1 106 \times I_1 0.58 = 61.5W$, $P_2 = E_2 110 \times I_2 0.62 = 68.2W$, 2ϕ total power = 130 W, Apparent power delivered to the transformers from the three-phase machine source. $400V \times 1.73 \times I_4 0.43 = 155 VA$ 3 ϕ total power = 155W.

The two resistance loads were removed from the circuit and connect to the transformer secondary were as shown in Figure2. While th primary windings were not disturb. Power supply was turn “ON” and was adjusted line-to-line voltage of 400 Vac

Voltages across each winding and the voltage across both windings in series were measure and record as: $E_1 = 120 Vac, E_2 = 121. Vac, E_3 = 172 Vac$ Voltage were return to zero and power supply switch “OFF”.

Figure2: two resistance loads removed from the circuit and connect to the transformer secondary

The E_1 and E_2 were observed to be 90° out of phase, and their sum E_3 were observed to be equal to the hypotenuse of right triangle with E_1 and E_2 of two sides.

E_3 using equation:

$$E_3 = \sqrt{(E_1)^2 + (E_2)^2}$$

$$(E_3)^2 = (E_1)^2 + (E_2)^2$$

$$E_3 = \sqrt{29041} = 170 Vac$$

$$E_{3\text{measure}} = 172V$$

E_3 Calculated =170V

The calculated and the measured value were in good agreement within 2 percent.

Figure.3. show the connection of capacitor run machine as two-phase machine. The capacitor shift the phase of one of the stator windings by 90 degree. Capacitor should not be connected in the circuit. Power supply was switch “ON” and line-to-line voltage was adjusted for of 400Vac and machines started running. Voltages across and the currents through, each of the stator windings were measure and record as: $E_1 = 110 Vac$, $I_1 = 1.2 A ac$, $E_2 = 112 Vac$, $I_2 = E_2 = 1.3 A ac$, Stator currents and Voltages were well balanced and the machine ran smoothly than before. Voltage returns to zero and power supply was switch “OFF”. The three-phase power source apparent power delivered is 3ϕ power=155VA 155, The apparent power by two-phase power delivered to the load is 2ϕ power=130VA. $(3\phi VA - 2\phi VA) / 2\phi VA = (155 - 130) / 130 = 25 / 130 = 0.19231 = 19.2\%$

Figure.3. Show the connection of capacitor runs motor as two-phase machine.

Figure4: Three-phase to two-phase transformation

The schematic connection of three-phase to two-phase transformation shown in figure4 illustrates the transformation of three-phase machine to two-phase power when one of the phases of the 400V input power were open and there will be no more two-phase machine output. Thus, 3 ϕ power has replaced 2 ϕ powers because, three-phase power is more economical to generate and transmit. Three-phase transmission lines use less wire than a two-phase line. The three-phase machines and control equipment are smaller, lighter in weight, and more efficient than single on two-phase equipment of the same rated capacity.

Figure 5: Connections of two single-phase transformers to obtain three-phase output from a two-phase power source show all windings and taps.

Three-phase machines are differing from a two-phase motor in that, it is smaller in size and may be used for industrial machines. A two-phase motor is a system that has two voltages at 90° apart, which is no longer in use nowadays. The alternator is composed of two windings placed at 90 degrees from each other. A three-phase motor is an electric machine that transforms electric power into mechanical energy by means of electromagnetic interactions. Some electric motors are reversible and they can transform mechanical energy into electric power acting as generators. The plastics industry manufactures polymer materials called plastics and offers services in plastics important to a range of industries, including packaging, building and construction, electronics, aerospace, manufacturing and transportation. It may be referred to as part of the chemical industry.

3.0 Three-phase to two-phase machine transformation Modeling

The rotor magnet can be considered as a loop of constant current source, i_m located at the stator direct axis. Any change in the magnetic flux of the rotor magnet will cause an induced electromagnetic force, resulting in a circulating current in the magnet [5, 6,]. The Resistance connected across the d-axis magnetization inductance shows the effect [3, 8]. There is no leakage inductance in the field. The permeability of the magnet material is almost unity, so the air gap inductance by the stator is the same in d and q axis and also no saturation will happen inside the machine. This model is similar to the conventional equivalent circuit of the synchronous machine, except there is no leakage inductance on the field [6, 8]. In addition, there is no difference between the back emf produced and that produced by an excitation coil. Hence the mathematical model of three-phase to two-phase machine

transformation is similar. The following assumption are made in the derivation, Saturation current is neglected although it can be taken into account by parameter changes, The induced emf is sinusoidal, Eddy current and hysteresis loss are negligible, there are no dynamics field current, there is no cage on the rotor. With these assumptions, the stator d, q equations of the three-phase to two-phase machine transformation in the rotor reference frame are; [3, 4, 5,]

$$V_q = R i_q + p \lambda_q + \omega_s \lambda_d \quad (3.1)$$

$$V_d = R i_d + p \lambda_d + \omega_s \lambda_q \quad (3.2)$$

Where

$$\lambda_q = L_q i_q \quad (3.3)$$

And

$$\lambda_d = L_d i_d + \lambda_{df} \quad (3.4)$$

V_d and V_q are the d, q, axis voltages, i_d and i_q are the d, q axis stator current, L_d and L_q are the d, q axis inductance, λ_d and λ_q are the d, q axis stator flux linkages. While R and ω_s are the stator resistance and inverter frequency, respectively. λ_{df} is the flux linkage due to the rotor magnet linking the stator.

The electric torque is

$$T_e = 3 p [\lambda_{df} i_q + (L_d - L_q) i_d i_q] / 2 \quad (3.5)$$

And the equation for the motor dynamic is

$$T_e = T_L + B \omega_r + J p \omega_r. \quad (3.6)$$

P is the number of pole pairs, T_L is the load torque, B is the damping coefficient, ω_r is the rotor speed, and J is the moment of the inertia. The inverter frequency is related to the rotor speed as follows:

$$\omega_s = p \omega_r. \quad (3.7)$$

The machines model is nonlinear as it contains product terms such as speed with i_d and i_q . Note that ω_r , i_q and i_d are state variables.

For dynamic simulation for the equation of the three-phase to two-phase machine transformation presented in equation (3.1) -(3.6) must be express in state-space form as shown in (3.8) -(3.10):

$$p \ i_d = (V_d - R \ i_d + \omega_s \ L_q \ i_q) / L_d \tag{3.8}$$

$$p \ i_q = (V_q - R \ i_q - \omega_s \ L_d \ i_d - \omega_s \ \lambda_{df}) / L_q \tag{3.9}$$

$$p \ \omega_r = (T_r - T_L - B \ \omega_r) / J. \tag{3.10}$$

The analysis of three-phase to two-phase machine transformation normally results in a good number of Simultaneous of non -linear equations which are algebraically complicated, however, and their solution

may be cumbersome. Mathematical transformations are tools which make complex system simple to analyze and solutions easy to find. Therefore, by these transformations, [3, 4], the analysis is greatly simplified by a change of variable for current, voltage and flux linkage. Figure 3.1 show a transformation from poly-phase to two-axis.

The d, q variable are obtained from a, b, c variable through the park Transform defines bellow:

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_q \\ v_d \\ v_o \end{bmatrix} = 2/3 \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & \cos(\theta - 2\pi/3) & \cos(\theta + 2\pi/3) \\ \sin(\theta) & \sin(\theta - 2\pi/3) & \sin(\theta + 2\pi/3) \\ 1/2 & 1/2 & 1/2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_a \\ v_b \\ v_c \end{bmatrix} \tag{3.11}$$

The a, b, c, variables are obtained from the d, q variables through the inverse of the park transform defined below:

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_a \\ v_b \\ v_c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & \sin(\theta) & 1 \\ \cos(\theta - 2\pi/3) & \sin(\theta - 2\pi/3) & 1 \\ \cos(\theta + 2\pi/3) & \sin(\theta + 2\pi/3) & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_q \\ v_d \\ v_o \end{bmatrix} \tag{3.12}$$

Note that, transformation apply equally well in current and in the linkages The total input power to the machine in term of the a, b, c variables

$$\text{Power} = v_a \ i_a + v_b \ i_b + v_c \ i_c \tag{3.13}$$

While in d, q variables,

$$\text{Power} = 3 \ (v_d \ i_d = v_q \ i_q) / 2 \tag{3.14}$$

For a balance system

Table 1: Three-phase to two-phase machine transformation parameters in simulation model

Stator leakage inductance of transformation	2.59Mh
q-axis rotor leakage inductance transformation	40.61Mh
d-axis rotor resistance transformation	0.8113Ω
q-axis rotor resistance transformation	1.6226Ω
q-axis magnetizing inductance transformation	40.69Mh
d-axis magnetizing inductance transformation	19.05mH
d-axis rotor leakage inductance transformation	18.97mH
Load torque transformation	7.63Nm
Motor inertial transformation	0.01986Kg m^2
Rated voltage transformation	230V(208V, 255V)

Source: [4, 5].

Figure6: Transformation Graph of Stator Currents /Time at operating condition

Figure7: Transformation Magnetic torque/ time at operating condition

Figure8: Transformation of Two phase machine stator currents/time at operating condition

Figure9: Transformation Two phase machines stator flux against time at operating condition

Figure10: Transformation Machines Rotor speed against time at operating condition

Figure 11: Transformation Graph of stator current / Time at varying operating condition

Figure 12: Transformation Graph of Load angle / Time at Varying Rated Voltage

Figure 13: Transformation Graph of Load Angle /time at Varying Equivalent Field Current

Figure 14: Transformation Graph of Machine Voltage / Stator Current

4.0 Conclusion:

The rotor magnet was considered as a loop of constant current source located at the stator direct axis. The change in the magnetic flux of the rotor magnet caused an induced electromagnetic force, resulting in a circulating current in the magnet. The Resistance that was connected across the d-axis magnetization inductance shows that there is no leakage inductance in the field. The permeability of the magnet material is almost unity, so the air gap inductance by the stator is the same in d and q axis and also no saturation happens inside the machine. This model is similar to the conventional equivalent circuit of the synchronous machine, except that there was no leakage inductance on the field. In addition, there was no difference between the back emf produced and that produced by an excitation coil. Hence the mathematical model of three-phase to two-phase machine transformation is similar. The following assumption are made in the derivation, Saturation current is neglected although it was be taken into account by parameter changes, The induced emf is sinusoidal, Eddy current and hysteresis loss are negligible, there are no dynamics field current, there is no cage on the rotor. With these assumptions, the stator d, q equations of the three-phase to two-phase machine transformation in the rotor reference frame are similar and balanced

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